

THE INFLUENCE OF PERSONAL VALUE, MOTIVATION AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT ON EMPLOYEES' WELL-BEING

ENENG NURLAILI WANGI

Faculty of Psychology, Universitas Islam Bandung, Indonesia. Email: nurlailiyunar@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Well-being has become one of the most influencing factors on organizational achievement capabilities. However, well-being itself is formed by various aspects including personal value, motivation, and organizational commitment. Nevertheless, research connecting these variables are rarely found. This research is aimed to measure the influence of personal value motivation and organizational commitment on employee's well-being. The design used in this research is causality design with a quantitative approach the sample of this research are the employees, lecturers, and teaching staff at 9 Islamic universities in Bandung, Indonesia. Related to efforts to measure the influence of Personal Values, Work Motivation and Organizational Commitment on Welfare, the researchers used inferential analysis with a Structural Equation Model (SEM) using the statistical method LISREL (Linear Structural Relationship). The results indicate that there is an influence of personal values, work motivation and organizational commitment to well-being that has met the criteria of goodness of fit. In addition, it was also found that the Achievement Value had a significant effect on work motivation. Personal achievement values and personal power values have an effect on work motivation in the lecturer group. Meanwhile, for the employees' group that has an effect on work motivation is the value of stimulation.

Keywords: Personal value, motivation, organizational commitment, well-being.

INTRODUCTION

Well-being has become an important concept in the world of work because it represents positive emotional thoughts and feelings which also important for the resilience level of an organization along with its development capability (Martin Seligman, 2011; Spreitzer & Porath, 2012). The effect of well-being and work performance is reciprocal; well-being leads to good performance, similarly, good performance leads to well-being (Warr & Nielsen 2018). Employee well-being in an organization is considered important because it does not only have an individual impact but has an overall impact on the organization, as stated by Wright (2017), employee well-being is a determining factor to understand employees and organizations better, for example to measure job satisfaction or employee retention decisions. This is supported by research of Robertson and Cooper (2011) which explains that prosperous employees can provide benefits to the organization such as high productivity, customer satisfaction, and the absence of disease.

Well-being is also one of the predictors that causes employee turnover (Brunetto, 2013), the lower the level of employees' well-being in an organization, the higher the chance that employees leave the organization. Job quality is also one of the factors that determine well-being that reflects "values in work and life." For example, employees that have high well-being level will be more eager to successfully achieve their life goals (Cooke, 2013). However,

employees' well-being is not only about job quality, but also the sense of respects in forms of both general and personal work benefits (Budd & Spencer, 2014). That is why it is also important to consider the other factors to determine the employees' well-being such as personal values, motivation, and organizational commitment.

Numerous studies show that there are significant relationships between personal values, well-being and behavioral intention (Sagiv and Schwartz, 2000; Hallowell, 1996; Fornell et al., 1996; Ryu et al., 2010; Emmons, 1991). Based on several researches (Sagiv and Schwartz, 2000; Sorthaix and Lönnqvist, 2014; Sorthaix and Lönnqvist, 2015; Bobowik et al., 2011), a person's subjective well-being may depend on that person's value priorities. This is also supported by Schwartz's (1992) research that value is closely related to well-being. On the other hand, autonomous motivation is also found to be positively associated with psychological well-being (Blais et al., 1993). These findings are supported by Nie et al. (2015) which confirmed that work motivation plays an important role on employees' well-being, with more autonomous forms of motivation being more beneficial.

Wright and Cropanzo (2000) discovered that well-being and job performance is significantly affecting each other, meanwhile Brunetto (2013) indicated that employee's well-being can significantly affect organizational commitment. These researches indicate that well-being and organizational commitment are reciprocally and significantly affect each other's. Personal values reflect what is vital to a person and consequently form a central part of an individual's identity that guides their actions (Jamaludin et al, 2016). According to Schwartz (1992), personal values act as life guidelines and the basis of evaluation on events, behaviors and individuals. Similarly, Ferssizidis et al. (2010) and Homer and Kahle (1988) argue that personal values influence human behavior, motivation and goals. Based on a number of researches (Sagiv and Schwartz, 2000; Sorthaix and Lönnqvist, 2014; Sorthaix and Lönnqvist, 2015; Bobowik et al., 2011), discovered that a person's value priority affects his subjective well-being.

Work motivation consists of internal factors of a person that is also influenced by external factors, which initiate and energize work-related behavior (Allen & Ebers, 2013). Employees' needs, wants, and goals, as well as various job characteristics are proven to be able to motivate individuals at work (Allen & Ebers, 2013). Motivation, depending on its nature, can be a protective or a vulnerable factor in explaining the influence of work environment factors on the psychological health of employees (Fernet, 2013), one of which is well-being. As stated by Nie (2015) autonomous motivation has a positive attachment to employee well-being. Mowday et al. (1982) defines organizational commitment as individual's identity and involvement in organization. Employees with high level of organizational commitment are more emotionally attached to their workplace (Meyer et al., 1991). Allen and Meyer (1990) also stated that employees with strong commitment tend to have more connection with their workplace and contribute more.

Apart from the abundant research on these topics; personal value, work motivation and organizational commitment, it is rare to find researches that simultaneously connect all three variables to well-being. Researcher discovered that there are researches that emphasize on the

significance of personal values, well-being and behavioral intention (Sagiv and Schwartz, 2000; Hallowell, 1996; Fornell et al., 1996; Ryu et al., 2010; Emmons, 1991), the significant influence of personal values on subjective well-being (Sagiv and Schwartz, 2000; Sortheix and Lönnqvist, 2014; Sortheix and Lönnqvist, 2015; Bobowik et al., 2011; Schwartz, 1992), the significant of work motivation on employees' well-being (Blais et al., 1993; Nie et al., 2015) and relationship between organization commitment and well-being (Wright and Cropanzo, 2000; Brunetto, 2012). Based on that this study aims to simultaneously examine the influence of personal values, work motivation, and organizational commitment on employees well-being.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Happiness and well-being are used interchangeably as terms that describe Positive Psychology (Seligman, 2002). Positive emotions (well-being and happiness) are divided into three types namely; (1) directed towards the past (satisfaction, contentment, pleased, and lucky), (2) the future (satisfaction, contentment, pleased, and lucky), and (3) the present (warmhearted, enthusiastic, cheerful, and interested) (Wright, 2017). The well-being view is divided into two namely; (1) Hedonic View: emphasizes life satisfaction and positive influences, and the absence of negative effects, (2) Eudaimonic View: emphasizes autonomy, growth, and actualization (Diener & Ryan, 2008; Diener, 2009). The definition of well-being used in this study uses an eudaemonic approach, which focuses on the components of thinking, meaning and self-realization. Namely, well-being as a fully functioning individual, focusing on meaning in life, and also self-realization (Deci & Ryan, 2008). Well-being is a concept. There is no single element that defines well-being, but each element contributes to it. More importantly, the elements of well-being are different: they are not simply self-reports of positive emotional thoughts and feelings, about how highly engaged an individual is, and how much meaning the individual has in life, as early theories of authentic happiness did. So the concept of well-being - not an entity of life satisfaction - is the main topic of positive psychology (Martin Seligman, 2011).

According to Seligman (2011) well-being is not something that only exists in the individual's mind, but is a combination of good feelings about oneself and feelings of having meaning in life, achievement and good relationships with others. A high level of well-being is known as flourishing, which is a combination of a pleasant feeling (good feeling) with well-functioning socially and psychologically. The concept used is well-being according to Seligman, known as flourishing, which is a high level of mental well-being (Effendy, 2016). The important elements in this well-being theory are summarized into PERMA, Positive Emotion (positive emotion), Engagement (involvement), Relationship (positive relationship), Meaning (meaning), and Accomplishment (achievement). These elements support employees' well-being. The existence of these five pillars exist will lead to prosperity (Seligman, 2013).

Well-being can be seen through the quality of work because the quality of work reflects "values in work and life". Employees with high well-being will achieve their life goals easier (Cooke, 2013). Well-being can occur when individuals evaluate their lives cognitively (overall) and evaluatively (specific aspects). Prosperous individuals have confidence in their ability to

organize, carry out tasks, achieve goals, produce things, and implement actions to display certain skills. A person's well-being can be influenced by the individual's ability to face difficulties, find solutions, solve problems and obstacles by changing their way of thinking (Dingemans & Henkens, 2015). The dominant aspects of life that affect well-being are religion, education, income, physical health, and self-esteem (Compton, 2005).

Values are motivational goals that influence attitudes, behavior and evaluations (Fischer and Boer 2016). Schwartz (2001) explains that value is a desired transsituational goal with various interests, which serves as action guidance. Relative value is abstract and serves as an evaluative standard that determines the desired goals and the means to achieve them (Rokeach, 1973; Kluckhohn, 1951; Rohan, 2000; Schwartz, 1992; Ferssizidis et al. 2010; Homer and Kahle, 1988). Personal values themselves reflect what is most important to a person and consequently form a central part of an individual's identity that guides his actions (Jamaludin et al., 2016). In addition, personal values provide guidelines for life and the basis for evaluating events, behaviors and individuals (Schwartz, 1992). Individuals are generally very satisfied with their values as they are getting closer to achieve their goals (Roccas et al., 2014).

The most productive and effective employees are the ones that are highly motivated and in good health. Such employees work with passion, produce high quality results, and work optimally (Fernet, 2013). In general, motivation is divided into two forms, namely autonomous and controlled motivation, both of which can affect the functioning and well-being of employees differently (Gagné and Deci, 2005). Autonomous motivation refers to volitional action, such as when employees engage in their work for the pleasure and inherent satisfaction they experience (intrinsic motivation) or because they personally support the importance or value of their work (identified regulation). Controlled motivation refers to behavior that is performed under internal or external pressure, such as when employees perform their jobs to gain a sense of self-worth or to avoid feelings of anxiety and guilt (closed regulation) or because they are pressured by demands, threats, or rewards by agents. external (external regulation) (Fernet, 2013).

Many studies have supported the existence of these forms of motivation and their different impacts on psychological functioning in various areas of life, including the workplace (Gagné and Deci, 2005). For example, autonomous motivation has been positively associated with psychological well-being (Blais et al., 1993), job satisfaction (Millette and Gagné, 2008), and work commitment (Fernet, 2011). In contrast, controlled motivation has been positively associated with negative consequences for workers, such as burnout (Fernet et al., 2008) and turnover intention (Richer et al., 2002). Motivation, depending on its nature, can be a protective or a vulnerable factor in explaining the influence of work environment factors on the psychological health of employees (Fernet, 2013). Employees' motivation are not only influenced by resources, but also by job demands, and it's simultaneously predicts positive and negative psychological consequences (Fernet, 2013). In SDT theory, work motivation is strongly influenced by the social context in which a person works (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Work motivation has been shown to play a considerable role in situations where work organizations impose limits on employees (Fernet, 2013).

Mowday et al. (1982) identifies the characteristics of organizational commitment as a strong desire to remain a member of the organization, a willingness to exert a high level of effort on behalf of the organization, and accept the organization's values and goals. Therefore, employee commitment is the psychological attachment of workers to their workplace (Meyer & Allen, 1997). Mowday et al. (1979) argues that employee commitment exists when organizational and individual goals are similar. Employees' commitment affects many behavioral outcomes, such as job satisfaction, job performance, absenteeism and turnover; it can be thought of as a motivating force, attitude, or set of behavioral intentions (Bateman & Strasser, 1984). Organizational commitment functions as a causal mechanism that links several positive features in the workplace, such as procedural fairness (Lavelle et al., 2009), mutual support (Ghosh, Reio, & Haynes, 2012), and OCB (Pooja et al., 2016). Meyer and Allen (1997) divide organizational commitment into three categories based on psychological states or mindsets related to commitment; (1) Affective Commitment, (2) Normative Commitment, and (3) Continuance Commitment.

Affective (want) commitment is an emotional attachment to the organization, this type reflects the attachment of affection to the target of commitment; normative (must) commitment, refers to a sense of obligation to the organization and a desire to remain in the organization, this reflects a sense of moral responsibility, and continuance (should) commitment refers to employees' perceptions that leaving the organization will incur high costs, this reflects the cause and the consequences of stopping an action. The three types have different impacts on behavior (Grabowski et al, 2019). Although Meyer and Allen (1997) and Meyer et al. (2002) suggest that affective and normative commitment specifically influence how an employee performs his job and discharges his responsibilities, we argue that in an educational context, lecturer commitment may be appropriately assessed in terms of their normative commitment to achieving student academic achievement and to maintaining positive student-student and teacher-student relationships.

The interests in the relationship between personnel values and well-being is on the rise (Fischer and Boer, 2016; Sortheix and Lönnqvist, 2014; Bobowik et al., 2011; Sagiv and Schwartz, 2000). The relationship between the subjects are significant (Sagiv and Schwartz, 2000; Hallowell, 1996; Fornell et al., 1996; Ryu et al., 2010; Emmons, 1991). Values are closely related to well-being: It is enough to think about one's values to increase a sense of "self-integrity" (Steele, 1988), and can act as measurement for a person's subjective well-being (Sagiv and Schwartz, 2000; Sortheix and Lönnqvist, 2014; Sortheix and Lönnqvist, 2015; Bobowik et al., 2011). The "value compatibility" perspective focuses on context, suggesting that values tend to lead to well-being when they match the values prevailing in one's social environment (Sagiv, Roccas, & Oppenheim, 2015). Nie (2015) discovered that work motivation plays an important role in employees' welfare, with a more autonomous motivation as determining factor. The more autonomous a person's motivation is, the more likely that person will experience greater well-being. Similarly, Chirkov, et al. (2003) and Blais et al. (1993) also mentioned that behaviors based on autonomous motivation were more likely to encourage persistence, performance, and greater well-being outcomes than controlled motivations.

The will to perform tasks will not be accurately directed without organizational commitment. Employees' organizational commitment plays a central role, especially to achieve organizational effectiveness because it encourages professional attitude that leads to numerous positive impacts towards the organization (Steers, 1987). According to Lambert et al. (2013) welfare is positively associated with affective commitment. Differently, the finding suggest that continuance commitment create a sense of being trapped and that leads to low satisfaction. Employees with stronger affective commitment to the organization actually experience better well-being than those who have a strong continuance commitment (Meyer, 2015). On the other hand, normative commitment shows lower association on well-being (Vandenberghe et al, 2015) because it has a sense of urgency which means that the employees continue to work only for survival.

METHODS

Participants and Procedure

The design used in this research is causality design. A quantitative approach is carried out to study a set of variables that are considered to have an effect on other variables but do not provide special treatment. Employees, lecturers, and teaching staff at Islamic universities in Bandung, Indonesia, are the objects of this research. The research population is 9 Islamic universities. A total of 1400 questionnaires were distributed both online and offline for six months. Of the total questionnaires distributed, 1007 questionnaires were returned and 721 were completely filled out. Prior to filling out the questionnaire, respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and asked to sign an informed consent form to ensure that they were volunteers and that their information was kept confidential. In addition, demographic data must also be filled in completely to identify backgrounds such as age, gender, education, religion, length of service, position.

Measures

Measurement of wellbeing was carried out using a standard measuring instrument developed by Julie Butler and Margaret L. Kern (2016) based on Seligman (2011) which consisted of 23 items. The scale is a semantic differential where respondents will read statements related to their well-being and choose which one best represents their condition, with scores ranging from 1 (least representative) to 10 (most representative). In addition to well-being, this instrument also measures developments that show good life experiences characterized by high levels of mental well-being. Employees are categorized as developing if all dimensions of PERMA are high (positive emotion, engagement, relationship, meaning accomplishment) and categorized as not developing if there is one dimension of PERMA profiler that is low. To measure personal value, this study uses the concept of commitment to the organization from Allen & Meyer (1997) and the concept of personal value from Schwartz and Bardi (2001). In this concept, personal values are divided into 9 components, namely self-direction, achievement, power, stimulation, hedonism, security, conformity, tradition, benevolence, and universalism. This instrument is a Likert model which explains the agreement on the given statement. In the variable of work motivation, the researcher uses the concept of Work Motivation from Locke

(1991). In this concept, work motivation is divided into 6 components, namely Actualization of Needs and Personality (ANP), Personal Goal Setting (PGS), Goal Support (GS), Goal-Directed Behavior (GDB), Goal Achievement, and Quality of Work Live. (QOWL), This instrument is a Likert model that explains the agreement on the given statement. Meanwhile, in measuring organizational commitment, this study uses the concept of organizational commitment from Allen & Meyer (1997). In this concept, commitment to the organization is divided into 3 components, namely affective commitment (6 items), normative commitment (6 items), and continuance commitment (6 items). Researched questionnaire. This instrument is a Likert model which explains the agreement on the given statement.

Data Analyses

The data analysis process was carried out to obtain themes that emerged in the perception and appreciation of teenagers regarding good or quality online friendships. Thus, the researcher uses thematic analysis, which is a method that aims to identify patterns or themes in qualitative data (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Maguire & Delahunt, 2017). The steps taken were the researcher tried to read the transcripts several times in order to understand the data, then carried out the initial coding process using sentence-by-sentence coding, which was then grouped into themes and sub-themes through a discussion process. Data related to interview transcripts was descriptively analyzed. The use of descriptive analysis is intended to provide an overview of personal values, work motivation, organizational commitment, and well-being as the variables that are the focus of this study. The components used as material for the application of descriptive analysis are company origin, company effectiveness category, gender category, marital status, education, and years of service.

Related to efforts to measure the influence of Personal Values, Work Motivation and Organizational Commitment on Welfare, the researchers used inferential analysis with a Structural Equation Model (SEM) using the statistical method LISREL (Linear Structural Relationship). Two reasons underlying the use of SEM is its ability to estimate the relationship between variables that are multiple relationships and the pattern of relationships between latent constructs (unobserved) and observed variables (indicator variables). Thus, it can be stated that this study consists of one exogenous variable, namely personal value (X_i) and 3 endogenous variables, namely work motivation (y_1), organizational commitment (y_2), and well-being (Y_3). Furthermore, these variables will be tested empirically using the SPSS-Release 17.0 software and LISREL version 8.70 software. The test uses the Standard Equation Modeling method using Latent Variable Score as data. Testing the measurement model using Confirmatory Factor Analysis with the Second Order method. This is done to reduce research errors and ensure that the results obtained are truly scientifically justifiable results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of Respondents

The explanation of these demographic factors includes age, gender, marital status, ethnicity, education, and the length of time an employee has worked at PTI in Bandung City for 721 respondents. The data that was collected from the respondents was dominated by respondents

from Unisba with a total percentage of 40.22%. Meanwhile, data contributions from other universities were obtained from UIN (21.77%), Uninus (12.62%), Muhammadiyah (16.78%), Al-Islam (4.57%), and Al-Ghifari (4.02%)

Demographic data of respondents based on gender shows the dominance of male employees with a percentage of 53.25% compared to female respondents with a percentage of 46.74%. The majority of respondents are those who are married to married employees with a percentage of 79.47%, followed by unmarried employees as much as 16.78%, and 3.74% are widowed/widowed. Based on education level, employees with diploma and bachelor degrees have the largest percentage, namely 47.3%, master education level reaching 40.22%, doctoral degree 9.3%, and high school graduates at 3.19%. As for the years of service, that can represent commitment to the organization, employees with less than 6 years dominate with a total percentage of 46.04%, 6-10 years reaching 12.20%, while those who work more than 10 years are around 41.74%. Meanwhile for Lecturers, it shows that they who work more than 10 years dominates with a percentage gain of 51.2%, 6-10 years with a percentage of 10.2%, and less than 6 years at 38.5%.

Descriptive analysis

Personal value consists of 10 dimensions and is operationalized into 40 statement items. In the following, the data for the average value and standard deviation of each indicator of the personal value variable are presented. Based on Figure 1, the highest personal values are found in the stimulation, benevolence and hedonism values. In the overall combination of respondents (Overall) it can be seen that the highest Personal Value is found in the stimulation value of 5.03 followed by the benevolence value of 4.94 and the hedonism value of 4.91. In general, employees have understanding, respect, tolerance, and protection for human and natural welfare, and have security, harmony, and stability in their environment and social relationships.

Figure 1: Average Score of Personal Value

Motivation consists of 6 dimensions and is operationalized into 42 statement items. In the following, the data on the average value and standard deviation of each indicator variable of work motivation are presented. As shown in Figure 2, the highest work motivation is found in the actualization of needs and personality, personal goal setting, goal achievement and goal support. In the overall combination of respondents (Overall) it can be seen that the highest work motivation is found in work motivation. Figure 2 shows that employees tend to agree with the dimensions of work motivation, goal directed behavior, and quality of work. In other words, employees have behavioral plans that lead to goals and the suitability of the values held by them with the implementation of work, challenges in achieving goals, safety and welfare in doing work.

Figure 2: Average Score of Work Motivation

Organizational commitment consists of 3 dimensions and is operationalized into 18 statement items. In the following, data on the average value and standard deviation of each indicator variable for organizational commitment are presented.

Figure 3: Average Score of Organizational Commitment

Figure 3 shows that the highest organizational commitment is found in the affective organizational commitment. If described, the value of affective organizational commitment in the lecturer group is 3.77. The value of affective organizational commitment in the employees group was 3.67, and the Affective Organizational Commitment of all respondents combined (Overall) had a value of 3.72. Based on the description of the data above, it shows that employees have awareness of the costs if they do not join the organization where they work. They tend to have a sense of responsibility for their work, which is influenced by psychological contacts and social environment.

Figure 4: Average Score of Well-Being

Employee Welfare consists of 5 dimensions and is operationalized into 23 statement items. In the following, data on the average value and standard deviation of each indicator variable for Employee Welfare are presented. From Figure 4, it can be seen that the highest Well-Being is found in the positive relationship factors, achievement, and meaning, which illustrates that respondents have positive feelings and can see the future with hope, enjoy the present, and see the past with joy. Employees also have something of value. Then, they use their strengths and talents for something bigger than themselves.

Structural Equation Model (SEM)

Structural model is a model that relates exogenous latent variables with endogenous latent variables or endogenous latent variables with endogenous latent variables.

Figure 5: Structural Model of the Influence between Variables on All Respondents

Description:

- PV : Personal Value
- MK : Work Motivation
- AC : Affective Commitment
- CC : Continuance Commitment
- NC : Normative Commitment
- WB : Well-Being

The conformity dimension has the greatest factor weight indicating that the conformity dimension is the strongest in reflecting the latent variable personal values, followed by the benevolence, security, achievement, stimulation, power, self direction, universalism, hedonism dimensions, and the last is the tradition dimension. The goal achievement dimension is the strongest in reflecting the latent variable of work motivation, followed by the personal goal setting, quality of work life, actualization of needs and personality, goal directed behavior, and finally goal support dimensions.

The dimension of positive emotion is the strongest in reflecting the latent variable of well-being, followed by the dimensions of achievement, positive relationship, engagement, and finally the dimension of meaning which is the weakest dimension in reflecting the latent variable of well-being.

Figure 6: Structural Model of the Influence between Variables on Lecturers

Description:

- PV : Personal Value
- MK : Work Motivation
- AC : Affective Commitment
- CC : Continuance Commitment
- NC : Normative Commitment
- WB : Well-Being

The dimensions of conformity and stimulation are the strongest in reflecting the latent variables of personal values, followed by the dimensions of benevolence, security, self direction, achievement, power, universalism, tradition, and finally the dimension of hedonism which is the weakest dimension in reflecting the latent variables of personal values. The goal achievement dimension is the strongest in reflecting the latent variable of work motivation, followed by the dimensions of personal goal setting, quality of work life, actualization of needs and personality, goal support and finally, the goal directed behavior dimension which is the weakest dimension in reflecting the latent variable of work motivation. The dimension of positive emotion is the strongest in reflecting the latent variable of well being, followed by the dimensions of achievement, positive relationships, engagement and lastly the dimension of meaning.

Discussion

In Figure 8 it can be seen that in the combination of all respondents the conformity value is shown through a series of behaviors that show behavioral control, control of tendencies and impulses that can attack social values so that there is conformity with social demands with the single values being politeness, obedience, self-discipline, respect. Parents and elders.

Furthermore, the value of security is shown through a series of behaviors to choose a safe environment and behavior that leads to balance and stability in socializing in society and in oneself. Its single values are family security, national security, social order, cleanliness, and returning the favor. While the value of benevolence is shown through the number of scores from a series of behaviors that show efforts to achieve prosperity in coexistence with others. The single values are helpful, honest, forgiving, loyal, and responsible which have a significant effect on well-being.

Another finding is that work motivation also has a significant influence on well-being. Meanwhile, in the combination of all respondents, Affective commitment leads to employees' emotional attachment and employee identification to their work. Employees who have affective commitment will remain in their jobs under any conditions. Employees who have an affective commitment will stay on the job because they want to (want to) do it. Employees who have a high affective commitment will have a strong desire to stay in their work, they have a desire to always develop in their work and normative commitment reflects a feeling of obligation to remain in the job. Employees with high normative commitment feel that they are ought to or feel a moral obligation to stay in their jobs, these employees will feel they have an obligation to be involved in their work activities and develop themselves, as a form of responsibility for their moral sense which has a significant effect. Against well-being. Overall, it can be seen that personal values, work motivation, and organizational commitment have a significant effect on well-being in all respondents combined.

Figure 8: Chart of All Respondents

Figure 9: Chart of Lecturers

The chart above explains that in the lecturer group, the conformity value is shown through a series of behaviors that show behavioral control, controlling tendencies and impulses that can attack social values so that they become conformity with social demands. The single values are politeness, obedience, self-discipline, and respect for people. Old and old. While the value of stimulation is shown through a series of behaviors that lead to awakening, great joy, pleasure in something new, and challenges in life. The singular values are courage, a varied life, and an exciting life.

Furthermore, regarding the benevolence value, which is shown through the number of scores from a series of behaviors, it shows an effort to achieve prosperity in coexistence with others. The single values are helpful, honest, forgiving, loyal, and responsible which have a significant effect on well-being. Meanwhile, work motivation has a significant influence on well-being. In the affective commitment of lecturer group, which leads to employees' emotional attachment and identification with their work. Employees who have an affective commitment will persist in their work under any conditions because they want to do so. Employees who have a high affective commitment will have a strong desire to stay in their work, they have a desire to always develop in their work so that it has a significant effect on well-being. Overall, it can be seen that personal values, work motivation, and organizational commitment have a significant effect on well-being in the Lecturer Group.

CONCLUSION

Based on this research, it can be concluded that there is an influence of personal values, work motivation and organizational commitment to well-being that has met the criteria of goodness of fit. In addition, it was also found that the Achievement Value had a significant effect on work motivation. Personal achievement values and personal power values have an effect on

work motivation in the lecturer group. Meanwhile, for the employees' group that has an effect on work motivation is the value of stimulation.

Overall, the Personal Values that influence the affective commitment (AC) are the achievement and power values. In the lecturer group, personal values that have an effect on affective commitment (AC) are achievement, stimulation and power values, while in the employees group, the influential values are conformity, universalism, hedonism, and power. In the combination of all respondents there is only one personal value that has an effect on CC, namely the tradition value. In the lecturer group, personal values that affect CC are tradition values and power values. While in employees, there is not a single personal value that has an effect on CC. Personal values that affect the normative commitment, (NC), are the values of tradition, achievement, and power. In the lecturer group, value of tradition, stimulation, and power. Meanwhile, in the employees group, the influential values are personal conformity and universalism values.

Personal values that affect employee welfare in the combination of all respondents are benevolence values. In the employees group, the influential personal value is the personal tradition value. work motivation has an effect on affective commitment (AC), continuance commitment (CC). normative commitment, (NC) is good for all respondents. In the combination of all respondents, work motivation has a significant effect on employee welfare. Meanwhile, in the employees group, work motivation did not significantly affect employee well-being. Affective commitment (AC), continuance commitment (COC). normative commitment, (NC) has a significant effect on welfare (WB).

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